

WOMEN AND GIRLS OF GENDER STEREOTYPES IMPACT ON LIFE

Yusupova Dildora Dilshatovna

doctor of philosophy (PhD), associate professor

Associate Professor of Public Security University of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Email: yu.dildora@list.ru

Annotation. The state describes the socio-cultural life of Turkestan women in the late XIX - early XX centuries, factors that led to the violation of ix rights, inflicted on them by an attacker of Islamic law by religious leaders. It also analyzes the negative consequences of gender stereotypes that arise today on the basis of historical processes.

Keywords. Gender, gender equality, gender stereotypes, relations between men and women, Muslim woman, Islamic Sharia, burqa, science and education.

Nowdays, there are a number of problems in the world in terms of ensuring gender equality, which still remains relevant. Such problems often persist in situations where men dominate women and use violence and force against them.

The worldview of the last century, that is, the trend of old age, continues in the minds of people in the form of gender stereotypes. In particular, gender stereotypes are widespread opinions in the society about the characteristics and behavior of representatives of different sexes, primarily men and women. Gender stereotypes are closely related to existing gender roles in a given society and serve to preserve and reproduce them. In particular, gender stereotypes help to perpetuate inequality¹.

¹https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Гендерные_стереотипы

Gender stereotypes are manifested in the tasks assigned to men and women in families. For example, a woman is busy with household chores in the family, takes on tasks such as raising children and fulfills the role assigned to her in the family. As a result, he is only busy with family affairs, putting a wall on his opportunities to express himself in terms of professional maturity. Realizing that only with the consent of her husband, she can show her professional potential, she mentally admits that she is dependent on him. This is where gender equality is undermined.

Social life in Turkestan proves that gender stereotypes exist not only today but also in the last century. For example, Abdurauf Fitrat, one of the modern enlighteners who lived in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, possessing religious and secular knowledge, expressed the following thoughts about the life, lifestyle, and male-female relations of the time he lived: are living exposed. We Turkestans think that our wives are beyond the scope of humanity, and we do not treat the poor as he would treat a man. We do not consider our wives worthy of favor, worthy of honesty and entitled to mercy. We consider it a matter of honor and pride to insult women, and we consider beating and maiming a manly virtue"².

It is a pity that the evils of the last century continue even today. If we do not achieve gender equality, these stereotypes will continue for many more generations and will be preserved in our national and religious values. As a result, the next generation will live in hatred of their ancestors.

After all, although the issue of protecting, caring for, and providing materially for a woman is recognized in Islam, the way of life of women in Turkestan is organized on the basis of the broken laws of the Sharia under the rather dogmatic views, it is not necessary to look down on women, and it is not necessary for them to acquire knowledge. , the thoughts and opinions of some foolish religious leaders, that they should only sit at home and do household chores, limited the rights and freedoms of women. In one of the Orenburg newspapers, a person named A.

² Фитрат А. Оила ёки оила бошқариш тартиби. – Т.: Маънавият, 2000. – Б. 33.

Fakhrutdinov criticized the article entitled "Muslim Women" by Iv. Podgorny, a person who did not know Sharia, that is a stranger to him. He tries to prove his opinion by quoting the following evidence from Sharia:

1. No woman can be forced into marriage. Even parents do not have any rights regarding the marriage of girls.

2. A woman, like a legal entity, does not need her husband's consent to own property, run a private household, sell or buy.

3. A woman's obligation did not go beyond family matters. Even the tasks of mowing grass and transporting water are entrusted to the land.

4. Marriage is only based on citizenship. A woman (virgin) has the right to leave her husband's house without losing any rights without the permission of the man if he does not fulfill any conditions at the time of marriage (she can also marry someone else).

5. Husbands do not have the right to disinherit their wives and daughters when they die...

6. At the time of marriage, the husband must pay the bride a "dowry". Dowry is her personal property.

7. During the divorce, the husband must provide for his ex-wife for up to three months, if she is pregnant until she gives birth.

8. If the husband cannot provide for his wife or does not provide her with the necessary means for her life, then at the request of the wife, the court will separate them and allow the wife to marry someone else.

9. According to Sharia, women are equal to men in all political, social and economic...

10. Even when women go to the side of the enemy during the battle, they are considered as deposits and are not killed or captured³.

³ ЎзР. МДА, ФИ-1009, рўйхат-1, иш-159, варақ-5.

A. Fakhruddinov refuted Iv. Podgorny by proving how a non-Muslim can talk about something he does not know, and how the issue of women is approached in Sharia.

To clarify the above points, there is no concept of enslavement of women in Islamic holy books either. But ignorant priests who have forgotten these wisdoms in Islam and dogmatic approach to Islamic enlightenment and law - high officials (such as Qazi Kalon, Sheikhu Islam) as well as their more ignorant executors in the local government system (chala mullahs) limit women's participation in social and cultural life in reality. led to limitation within. The fact that women do not know their rights is evidenced by their lack of knowledge. After all, if there is no gender equality in society, a new way of thinking and a new way of living cannot be achieved in such a society.

In the last century, the issue of women is the most important issue, it is a sore point of the society, many opinions have been raised by local scholars about educating and bringing them out from within. However, the matter did not yield any result, as these thoughts without action continued to drag on day after day as they did not show their practical results.

The lament of women who are deprived of the source of knowledge under the burqa was heard in the letters of Hanifa Oysieva "The wound was opened" and "Give us a way" by Mrs. Khayriya. For example, in the letter "Yara achildi": "The wishes of our women must be in accordance with the requirements of Islam. Islamic rulings should be applied to women. Otherwise, if our women die, then the nation will perish, because the well-being of the nation depends on women,"⁴ says Hanifa Oysieva. When he reads that women are deprived of the light of knowledge, their eyes are closed and they cannot breathe, it is not difficult to feel that they are suffocated under the veil.

⁴ ЎзР МДА ФИ-1009, рўйхат-1, иш-159, варақ-17.

Hanifa Oysiyeva, who understood that women are the real educators of the nation, said: "Unless a part of the nation learns to read and write, the other half cannot be free."⁵ Therefore, that we cut the woman under the burqa off from education shows that not only the upbringing of children but also the future of the nation has been axed. In the second letter sent by Ms. Khairiya, "If the nation wants to be saved, it should educate its girls is required by religion, sharia, humanity and time," he continued, "Educate us, and after that, make us nationalists, patriots, and so forth demand children"⁶, - he cites the example of women not being able to educate the next generation, being left behind by the backward, uneducated age, coz a man lives if a woman from birth to death. In fact, as long as men forget the role of women who help men mentally and spiritually in any situation, men live as unhappy as women.

It is no exaggeration to say that in the last century in Turkestan, the wrong interpretation of religion by some Sharia leaders and religious fanatics created the ground for women's rights to be wrapped in burqas, to have no place in society, and to be thrown into a deep abyss in an illiterate manner. After all, as our President noted: "The cultural level of any society on earth is determined by its attitude towards women"⁷.

It is clear from the above points that the violation of gender, i.e. male-female relations in society, disregard for women who have sensitive behavior and feelings, and failure to evaluate them correctly has led to the violation of human rights.

We think it is permissible to quote the following words of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "A girl child is the mistress of the future family, the owner of our future.

⁵ ЎзР МДА ФИ-1009, рўйхат-1, иш-159, варақ-17.

⁶ ЎзР МДА ФИ-1009, рўйхат-1, иш-159, варақ-17.

⁷ Мирзиёев Ш. Миллий тараққиёт йўлимизни қатъият билан давом эттириб, янги босқичга кўтарамиз. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2017. – Б. 345.

The way we educate them today, tomorrow they will educate our new generation"⁸. It is also known from the thoughts of our head of state that the girl child is embodied in our eyes not only as a progenitor but also as a person who determines the future of our country. The more we pay attention to it, the more our country will progress.

Based on the above considerations, it is appropriate to make the following recommendations:

First, one should not forget that the future role of the state depends on the knowledge of the women of this society;

Secondly, it is necessary to draw a correct conclusion from the evils of the past century and not to repeat mistakes and shortcomings;

Thirdly, it is appropriate to understand that the wrong interpretation of Sharia law can cause women to become victims of violence in society;

Fourthly, it should not be forgotten that Islam has a very beautiful solution to the issue of gender equality.

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⁸ Мирзиёев Ш. Миллий тараққиёт йўлимизни қатъият билан давом эттириб, янги босқичга кўтарамиз. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2017. – Б. 350.